

Stability of Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with Esters of Salicylic Acid

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The stepwise stability constants of complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II) with methylsalicylate, ethylsalicylate or phenylsalicylate have been determined. The effect of temperature and ionic strength has been studied. The thermodynamic stability constants are obtained at 25°. The stability order is Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) and methylsalicylate > ethylsalicylate > phenylsalicylate. The higher values of stability constants suggest that the complexes are chelate in nature.

THE stabilities of the chelates of methylsalicylate with some metal ions of the first transition series in aqueous solutions were reported by Perrin¹. The stabilities of ethylsalicylate complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Hg(II) are known in literature². The stabilities and thermodynamic functions of the complexes of Mn(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with esters of salicylic acid have been published from our laboratory^{3,4}. A systematic study of the stabilities of the complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II) with methylsalicylate, ethylsalicylate or phenylsalicylate is reported in this paper.

Experimental

Bjerrum Calvin pH titration technique^{5,6}, as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷, has been used for investigations. The stability constants of the complexes have been determined at 25° and various ionic strengths viz. 0.05 M, 0.075 M, 0.10 M and at 35° with an ionic strength of 0.05 M in aqueous ethanol 50 : 50 (v/v). The ionic strength was adjusted by adding NaClO₄ solution as an inert electrolyte. In order to fulfil the condition of maximum coordination number, metal to ligand ratio was kept at 1 : 5. Since the titrations were carried out in aqueous ethanol system appropriate corrections were applied to the measurements to get the actual pH⁸. The following three solutions were titrated against a standard alkali (0.1 M KOH).

- (A) 2.0 ml of 0.05 M HClO₄
(B) A + 2.0 ml of 0.05 M ligand
(C) B + 2.0 ml of 0.01 M metal ion.

The initial volume in each case was 20 ml containing aqueous ethanol system 50 : 50 (v/v). The titrations were carried at 25 ± 0.1° and 35 ± 0.1° in a constant temperature bath.

Results and Discussion

The esters of salicylic acid are weak acids due to the OH group. The values of $\bar{n}_A$, K_1^H , $\bar{n}$ and pL

were calculated by the usual relationships⁹. The formation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL . The value of $\bar{n}$ does not go beyond 2 in any case for the metal complexes. This indicates the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF ESTERS OF SALICYLIC ACID IN ALCOHOL : WATER SYSTEM 50 : 50 (v/v) AT 25°

Ester	Metal ion	Ionic strength <i>M</i>	log K ₁	log K ₂
Methyl salicylate	Co(II)	0.000	5.70	4.50
		0.050	4.95	3.83
		0.750	4.80	3.72
		0.100	4.70	3.62
		0.050*	5.62	4.82
	Ni(II)	0.000	6.80	4.60
		0.050	5.30	3.85
		0.075	5.20	3.75
		0.100	4.90	3.65
		0.050*	5.75	4.89
	Cu(II)	0.000	14.62	13.00
		0.050	9.37	8.50
		0.075	8.25	7.45
		0.100	7.00	6.37
		0.050*	7.43	7.00
Ethyl salicylate	Co(II)	0.000	5.60	4.40
		0.050	4.90	3.80
		0.050*	5.14	4.50
	Ni(II)	0.000	6.40	4.50
		0.050	5.16	3.82
		0.050*	5.17	4.77
	Cu(II)	0.000	8.90	8.10
		0.050	6.90	6.40
		0.050*	6.70	6.20
Phenyl salicylate	Co(II)	0.000	5.00	4.30
		0.050	4.55	3.80
		0.050*	4.60	3.87
	Ni(II)	0.000	5.60	4.40
		0.050	4.87	3.80
		0.050*	4.90	4.35
	Cu(II)	0.000	7.70	7.20
		0.050	6.55	6.05
		0.050*	6.30	5.78

* at 30°.

stability constants for the complexes were obtained by half $\bar{n}$ method and linear extrapolation method⁹. The values obtained by both the methods are in good agreement. The average values at different temperatures and ionic strengths are given in Table 1. The thermodynamic stability constants at 25° were obtained by plotting $\log K_n$ values against $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolating to zero ionic strength. These are also given in Table 1.

A perusal of the values of the stability constants shows that there exists the stability order $\text{Cu(II)} > \text{Ni(II)} > \text{Co(II)}$ with regards to the nature of the metal ions. This sequence of stability constants agrees with the Irving-Williams natural order¹⁰ and other orders confirmed by several workers^{11,12}.

Regarding the nature of the ligands, the stability order of the complexes is methylsalicylate > ethylsalicylate > phenylsalicylate. The value of $\log K_1^H$ (the proton-ligand stability constant) has been found to decrease on increasing the bulk of the group R in $\text{R-OOCC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}^8$. This explains the descending stability order of the complexes with increasing bulk of R in the esters. A comparison of the stabilities at 25° and 35° shows that the effect of rise of temperature on the stability of the complexes becomes less and less pronounced in going from methylsalicylate through ethylsalicylate to phenylsalicylate.

Another important factor influencing the stability is ionic strength of the medium. It is apparent from the stabilities at 25° with different ionic strengths (Table 1); the stabilities record a decrease with an increase of ionic strength. This is in accordance with the earlier conclusions of Debye¹³. In media of higher ionic strength the metal ions are shielded from the ligands by the other ions present. This results in low rates of combination of the metal ions with the ligands.

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